

Growth and Characterization of MFS and MFIS Preliminary Prototype Device with $\text{Ba}_{0.7}(\text{Sr})_{0.3}\text{TiO}_3$ Thin Film for Non-volatile Memory Device Application

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Abstract

$\text{Ba}_{1-x}(\text{Sr})_x\text{TiO}_3$ ($x=0.3\text{mol}$) (BST) powder was formulated and prepared by solid state mixed oxide route. The phase evaluation and structural properties of BST powder were studied by X-ray Diffractometer (XRD) with the Bragg angle between 10° to 70° . The microstructure grains growth of the BST powder was investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). $\text{Ba}_{1-x}(\text{Sr})_x\text{TiO}_3$ film was formed on naked p-Si (100) and oxide layer buffered p-Si (100) substrates by spin coating technique. After spin coating, subsequent annealing (500°C to 700°C) in oxygen and atmospheric ambient was followed to form the BST oxide film from BST sol solution coating. SEM investigation (planner and cross-sectional views) was carried out to examine the surface morphology and film thickness. Capacitance and voltage (C-V) characteristics of MFS and MFIS prototype devices were observed.

Key words: BST sol solution, Surface morphology, C-V characteristic, MFS, MFIS

Introduction

Ferroelectricity is a spontaneous electric polarization of a material that can be reversed by the application of an external electric field. Ferroelectric crystals often show several transition temperatures and domain structure hysteresis, much as do ferromagnetic crystals (Website 1). Barium carbonate powder is dense and white and is manufactured mainly from the mineral barite (BaSO_4) using a floating process. There are several crystalline forms of BaCO_3 , alpha is the most stable (Website 2). Strontium carbonate (Strontianite) is a rare carbonate mineral and one of only a few strontium minerals. Color is white, colorless, gray yellowish or greenish. Crystals are transparent to translucent. Crystal system is orthorhombic (Website 3). Titanium dioxide, also known as titanium (IV) oxide or titania, is the naturally occurring oxide of titanium, chemical formula TiO_2 . Titanium dioxide is a complex material because it opacifies, variegates, and crystallizes glazes (Website 4). Barium strontium titanate (BST) is a solid solution perovskite with a field – dependent permittivity. In recent years, there has been a strong interest in thin film BST, first for dynamic random access memory and later for microwave applications (Pervez *et al*, 2004).

Materials and Methods

Process for the synthesis of fine BaTiO_3 powder utilizes a wide variety of methods including a solid-state reaction, co-precipitation (citrate), oxalates, hydrothermal synthesis, alkoxide hydrolysis and metal-organic processing. The solid state reaction method is the traditional method for preparing BaTiO_3 powders by mixing the starting materials, usually titanium dioxide and barium carbonate and calcinations them at an element temperature around 1200°C . However, the solid-state reaction method tends to result in a significant amount of agglomeration, poor chemical homogeneity and undesirable secondary phase such as BaTi_2O_5 (Yoon *et al*, 2002). A mechano-chemical activation by the heavy milling is the key step in this recent process which alters the physicochemical properties of the starting materials and the

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mechanism of synthesis. Moreover, it is expected that the fine starting materials enhance the solid-state reaction due to their high activity and hence decrease the reaction temperature and final particle size. Conventional ball mills and attrition mills adopting a discontinuous operating system have been used for a long time for the purpose of milling (Yoon *et al*, 2006).

Multi-Step Reaction Mechanism

Homogeneous BaTiO₃ particle were formed gradually by the reaction between Ba₂TiO₄ and TiO₂ due to the continuous diffusion. This multi-step reaction mechanisms were

Overall reaction was $\text{BaCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2 \rightarrow \text{BaTiO}_3 + \text{CO}_2$

Ba(Sr)TiO₃ Powder Preparation

The starting chemicals were barium carbonate (BaCO₃), strontium carbonate (SrCO₃) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) of reagent grades. Very fine BaCO₃ and SrCO₃ particles were helpful in increasing the number of contact points with other starting materials and on their easy decomposition at low temperature. Thus physical milling technique was used to get the fine BaCO₃ and SrCO₃ particles. Ball-mill was used to reduce the particle size of BaCO₃ and SrCO₃ separately. Air-jet milling was performed to get the moisture-less particle of BaCO₃ and SrCO₃ powders. Polycrystalline sample of Sr-doped barium titanate was prepared using calcination method at the elevated temperature about 1200°C for 1.5 h. The BST powder was sieved with 3-stage mesh-sieve (100 mesh, 250 mesh and 400 mesh) to form the uniform particle size while the ball-mill was employed to reduce the particle size. Air-jet mill was also used to get chemical homogeneity and moisture-less BST powder.

The illustrations of Ball-mill, Air-jet mill and 3-stage mesh-sieve were shown in Figure 1 (a-c). The preparation steps of BST powder was given in Figure 2 as a block diagram.

Fig. 1(a). Photograph of Ball-milling

Fig. 1(b). Photograph of Air-jet milling

Fig. 1(c). Three-step mesh sieve

Figure 2. Flow diagram of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder preparation

Powder Analysis by XRD, SEM and TG-DTA

Figure 3 showed XRD pattern of Ba(Sr)TiO₃. In the pattern, lower site showed the standard figure and upper site of the profile showed the observed peak. The degree of 2θ indicated between 10° and 70°. On the pattern, there were 7 standard reflections and 7 observed reflections. It was found that standard reflections were a perfect match for observed reflections and it showed that strontium was absolutely occupied by barium titanate. The most dominant peak was (110) reflection and the 2θ degree of all observed peak were 22.282°, 31.7°, 39.06°, 45.478°, 51.159°, 56.659° and 66.258° respectively.

As the detailed analysis, most of the peaks were formed with left-shifted to the standard reflections. The most dominant peak was formed with unidentified co-existing peak and it might be due to the formation of secondary phase such as BaTi₂O₅. The unnecessary peaks appeared and it was due to impurities during annealing period. As a result, Ba(Sr)TiO₃ was absolutely formed at a given temperature. The crystallite size (nano particle size) of BST specimen could be calculated by Debye-Scherrer formula and it was evaluated to be 25 nm.

$$G = \frac{0.899 \times \lambda}{FWHM \times \cos \theta_B}$$

Where,

G = crystallite size, $\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$

FWHM = Full width at half maximum of dominant peak (110)

$$\theta_B = \frac{1}{2} \times 2\theta \text{ of dominant peak (110)}$$

Figure 3. XRD pattern of BST powder

Two types of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder (before and after mesh-sieving) were analyzed by SEM technique. The observed SEM photographs of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder were described at Figure 4 (a & b). Crack-free and fine grain were clearly observed on both SEM microphotographs. The grain sizes were estimated to be 1.53μm and 1.7μm for Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder with and without mesh sieving. Both microstructures were oriented toward left side and non-uniform grain distribution. Some pores and grain growth pattern were formed among the crystalline grains.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. SEM microphotograph of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ powder (a) before and (b) after mesh-sieved

Phase Transition (ϵ_r -T characteristics)

To identify the phase transition of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ sample, ϵ_r -T characteristic was studied by capacitor equation,

$$C = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \frac{A}{d}$$

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{Cd}{\epsilon_0 A}$$

where, ϵ_r = relative dielectric constant, $\epsilon_0 = 8.85 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m

C = capacitance, A = area of electrode, d = thickness of disk

Temperature Dependence of Charge Storage Capacity

Dispersion of capacitance with respect to annealing temperature was shown in Figure 5. Measurement was made at applied frequency of 20 kHz with zero bias voltage. Two distinct states were significantly formed on C-T characteristic curve. From the C-T curve, it was observed that the capacitance was temperature dependence.

Figure 5. Temperature Dependence of Charge Storage Capacity

Figure 6. The relative dielectric constant and temperature variation curve

Figure 6 indicated the ϵ_r -T variation curve. Two distinct states were also formed. The graph nature was almost the same as that of C-T graph. The phase transition temperature changed from ferroelectric phase to paraelectric phase was about 133°C and found to be larger than the reported value of BaTiO_3 . The photograph of Impedance Analyzer (LCR meter) with measurement system was shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Investigation of capacitance by using heater controller

Preparation of $\text{Ba}(\text{Sr})\text{TiO}_3$ Sol Solution

To prepare the BST sol solution, laboratory-grown BST powder and 2-methoxyethanol ($\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$) solvent were used. They were mixed and stirred with magnetic stirrer with constant speed (600 rpm) for 5 h to obtain homogeneous BST sol solution of 0.2 M. The sol solution was refluxed at 110°C for 4 h in a three-neck flask assembly to react the BST powder and boiled $\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ solvent. BST sol solution was formed after being cooled down to room temperature. It was aged for 5 h to enhance the viscosity.

Substrate Preparation

Defect-free and polished p-Si (100) (1cm x 1cm) wafer was used as a substrate. To get the naked surface and to remove the native oxide and contamination, ultrasonic cleaning process was made as follows:

- The Si wafer was washed in boiling acetone (60°C), then in boiled propanol (50°C) for 5 min to remove greasy film.
- It was immersed in nitric acid HNO₃ for 3 min in order to remove ionic contamination.
- It was etched in buffered hydrofluoric acid (34.6% NH₄F: 6.8% HF: 58.6% H₂O) for 2 min to remove oxide film.
- It was cleaned in DIW and dried on flat-oven at 100°C in a few minute.
- Finally, it was purged with N₂ gas and clean Si-wafer was formed.

Thin Film Deposition (Single Wafer Spin Processor)

SiO₂ layer (insulating layer) was thermally formed on p-Si (100) substrate (1cm x 1cm). BST sol solution was deposited and both substrates (Si & SiO₂/Si) by Single Wafer Spin Processor. The operation condition was placed on Fragment Adapter and the BST sol solution was poured onto substrate. The spin speed or rotational speed was set 4000 rpm and spinning time was 30 sec. To change the sol coating into oxide film, they were annealed at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C in O₂-atm for 1h respectively. Eventually, BST/Si and BST/SiO₂/Si cells were formed at different process temperatures.

Figure 8. Single wafer spin processor (WS -400BZ-6NPP/LITE)

Table 1. Spin-coating Condition

Spin speed	4000 rpm
Spinning time	30 sec
N ₂ gas pressure	60 Psi
Vaccum	25.3 (inches of Hg)

Figure 9. Block diagram for preparation of BST/Si & BST/SiO₂/Si thin films

Figure 10. Structures of MFS and MFIS

SEM Image of BST/ Si Film

Figure 11(a~c) showed the SEM image of BST/Si film (500°C, 600°C, 700°C) at 10,000 photo magnification. We measured the grain size by using well known bar code system, drawing cross bars of same dimensions as provided scale and measuring number of interesting grains across them. The grain size of BST/Si microphotographs were examined to be 0.35 μm , 0.37 μm and 0.5 μm at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C. From the results, the grain size increased and porosity decreased as the process temperature increased from 500°C to 700°C. Thus, this result suggested that the improvement of remanent polarization density (P_r) might be attributed to increasing grain size, because it was known that grain growth in film was effective in improving P_r .

Figure 11. SEM microphotograph of BST/Si films (a) at 500°C, (b) 600°C and (c) 700°C

Film Thickness of BST/Si Film

The film thickness was obtained by X-sectional SEM image and shown in Figure 12 (a~c). The film thickness was found to be 20.4 μm , 24.5 μm and 28.2 μm for BST/Si film at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C, respectively. In this range of temperature, it was found that the higher the temperature, the greater the film thickness.

Figure 12. SEM microphotographs of BST/Si film thickness at (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C and (c) 700°C

SEM Image of BST/ SiO₂/Si Film

Morphological changes in the films on SiO₂/Si substrate structure observed by SEM and Surface micrography of the films were shown in fig.13 (a~c) . From the results, the grain sizes were observed to be 0.26 μm, 0.21 μm and 0.32 μm for BST/SiO₂/Si film at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C. The surface morphology was examined to be little different. The exact and crowded spherical smooth grain BST films were detected. However, little rough spherical boundaries of grains were significantly large grain sizes and uniform distribution over the given substrate surface area of less magnification image, one could be predicted that the BST film on SiO₂/Si substrate was of integrity and non-cracking.

Figure 13. SEM microphotograph of BST/SiO₂/Si film at (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C and (c) 700°C

Film Thickness of BST/SiO₂/Si Film

The X-sectional SEM image of BST/SiO₂/Si film was given as Fig 14 (a~c). The film thickness was found to be 25.2 μm, 27.5 μm and 29.3 μm for the BST/SiO₂/Si film at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C.

Figure 14. SEM microphotograph BST/SiO₂/Si film thickness at (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C and (c) 700°C

Electro-less Nickel plating

Ni-conductive layer was formed on front and back (counter) sides of BST film by electro-less Ni-plating. The exposed area ($0.4\text{cm} \times 0.4\text{cm}$) was set on front side and remaining area was covered with mask. The exposed area ($0.6\text{cm} \times 0.6\text{cm}$) was also set on back side of the p-Si (100) wafer. After that, Ni-conductive layers were formed by electro-less Ni-plating. After 3 min, it was taken from Ni-solution and dried at room temperature. After removing the mask, Ni-conductive layer was formed. Cu-wire was soldered on front and counter conductive layer. The flow diagram of Ni-layer formation was shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Flow diagram of Ni-layer formation

C-V Measurement

Capacitance and voltage characteristics of MFS (Ni/BST/Si) and MFIS (Ni/BST/SiO₂/Si) cells were measured by Impedance Analyzer (Quch Tech: 1730).

Figure 16. C-V characteristic of BST/Si films at (a) 500°C, (b) 600°C and (c) at 700°C

Figure 17. C-V characteristic of BST/SiO₂/Si film at (a) 500°C, (b) 600 °C and (c) 700°C

Figure 16 (a~c) mentioned the C-V characteristic curves of MFS designs recorded at applied frequency of 100 kHz. The C-V characteristics of MFIS designs at different process temperatures were shown in Figure 17(a~c). In all cases, the bias voltage was cycled between ± 1 , ± 2 , ± 3 , ± 4 and ± 5 V. At -5V, the capacitor developed 2 depletion layers under the gate and therefore had finite capacitance reducing the device capacitance. The capacitance cycled counterclockwise, which were consistent with a polarization switching mechanism and contrary to the hysteresis developed by charge injection. On C-V curve, the voltage gap was significantly formed and it might be due to the non-volatile memory nature of BST film. The hysteresis gap, the memory window (MW) was measured on C-V curve. The memory windows (MW) were 0.42V, 0.55 V, 0.75 V for MFS memory capacitor at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C. The memory windows (MW) for MFIS capacitors were 0.68 V, 0.75 V, 1.12 V at 500°C, 600°C and 700°C respectively. Thus the counter clockwise C-V hysteresis became larger with increasing process temperature. This fact indicated that the increase in remanent polarization of ferroelectric capacitor. Table 2 showed the dispersion of MW with respect to process temperature for all fabricated cells.

Table 2. Dispersion of MW as a Function of Process Temperature

Process Temp (°C)	Memory Window (V)	
	MFS	MFIS
500	0.42	0.68
600	0.55	0.75
700	0.75	1.12

The threshold voltage, flat-band voltage occurred at sweep up and down directions (voltage increasing & decreasing directions) were measured on C-V curves. The measured values for both devices were collected and listed in Table 3.

Table 3. The Change in V_{TH} and V_{FB} with respect to Process Temperature

Process Temp (°C)	V _{TH,U} (V)		V _{TH,D} (V)		V _{FB,U} (V)		V _{FB,D} (V)	
	MFS	MFIS	MFS	MFIS	MFS	MFIS	MFS	MFIS
500	1.40	1.75	1.12	1.12	-1.25	-1.25	-1.87	-2.00
600	1.56	2.00	0.97	1.25	-1.50	-1.37	-2.10	-2.60
700	1.75	2.30	1.00	1.31	-1.10	-1.40	-1.88	-2.12

V_{TH,U} = threshold voltage (sweep-up)
 V_{TH,D} = threshold voltage (sweep-down)
 V_{FB,U} = flat-band voltage (sweep-up)

$V_{FB,D}$ = flat-band voltage (sweep-down)

Conclusion

Fabrication and characterization of Ba(Sr)TiO₃ specimen have been successfully investigated. From XRD result, it was found that the modifier, Sr was totally occupied by Ba-site (A-site). In addition, the peak (110) was rather sharp, which indicated the observed Ba(Sr)TiO₃ had polycrystalline nature. As a result of powder analysis, BST powder was crystalline and non-cracking morphology. As a SEM result, optimized process, the crack of film could be effectively avoided, consequently, the preparation of film was controllable. The C-V characteristics exhibited counter clockwise hysteresis behavior, indicating the ferroelectric polarization reversal. The capacitance value (charge storage capacity) widened with increase in process temperature for all devices. Thus, our experimental results indicated that the preliminary prototype cell with Ba(Sr)TiO₃ film is quite promising candidate for non-volatile memory device application. On the other hand, the laboratory-prepared MFS and MFIS multilayer configurations with Ba(Sr)TiO₃ film can be used as 1C of FeRAM (Ferroelectric Random Access Memory) application.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge our deep gratitude to Professor Dr Khin Mar Kyu, Head of Department of Physics, Dagon University and Professor Dr May Myint Si, Department of Physics, Dagon University, for allowing and encouraging us to present this paper.

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Online Materials

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